

Manichaeans

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Religious Group, Anatolian Religions, Greek, Dualist Tradition, Mixed Language, Indo-European, Zoroastrianism, Persian-Indic, Iranian Religion, Language, Mystery Religion

Manichaeism was a dualistic religious movement that was founded in Persia in the 3rd century CE by Mani, who was known as the Apostle of Light or the supreme illuminator. Even though Manichaeism was broadly considered as a Christian heresy, which many Christian Fathers opposed with their writings, it was in fact a religion per se. The coherence of its doctrines and the rigidity of the structure and institutions, preserved throughout its history a unity and unique character. The founder of Manichaeism was Mani. He was of Iranian origin, born in 216 near Seleucia-Ctesiphon (southern Babylonia), in modern day Iraq, in the Parthian Empire. It is believed that his parents were members of the Jewish Christian Gnostic sect known as the Elcesaites, a sect active between 100 and 400 CE originating in the Transjordan region. Mani considered himself as the final successor in a long line of prophets, from Adam to Jesus Christ, also including Buddha and Zoroaster. His views on other, earlier religious systems was critical, since he believed that the effectiveness of religious experience, as well as the transcendental experiences were limited. He therefore regarded himself as the carrier of a universal message destined to replace any other religion. In his effort to prevent corruption and to ensure doctrinal unity, he recorded his teachings in writing and gave them canonical status during his lifetime. At the age of 24, after receiving a divine order that imposed him to publicly proclaim his doctrines, Mani began preaching throughout the Persian empire. Mani pursued to establish an ecumenical and universal religion that would integrate all the teachings of previously revealed truths, particularly those of Zoroaster, Buddha, and Jesus. However, beyond mere syncretism, it sought the proclamation of a truth that could be perceived in different forms. Manichaeism, therefore, resembles Iranian and Indian religions, as well as Christianity, Buddhism, and Taoism, depending on the context and in accordance with the different cultural background into which it spread. Mani's missionary activity was unconstrained since he had the support of the Sasanian Empire. However, he failed to win the favor of the next generation of Persian royalty, the Emperor Bahram I, and with the disapproval of the Zoroastrian clergy Mani possibly died imprisoned (perhaps in 276-277) awaiting execution- his followers called that period the "Passion of the Illuminator" or Mani's "crucifixion". From its very first steps, the Manichaean church begun an active missionary activity to convert the world. Mani encouraged the translation of his writings into other languages and organized an extensive mission program. Manichaeism, hence, quickly spread west into the Roman Empire. From Egypt it moved across northern Africa, managing to convert figures such as the young Augustine, and even reached Rome in the early 4th century. It was during that century that the Manichaean expansion in the West reached its peak, establishing churches in southern Gaul and Spain, while it has also spread to the eastern provinces of the Persian Sasanian empire. The expansion of the Manichaeans to the East had already begun in the 7th century, after China's conquest of East Turkistan. A Manichaean missionary reached the Chinese court in 694, and in 732 an edict gave the religion freedom of worship in China. When East Turkistan was conquered in the 8th century by the Uyghur Turks, one of their leaders adopted Manichaeism. Manichaeism thus remained the state religion of the Uyghur kingdom until its overthrow in 840. Manichaeism probably survived in East Turkistan until the Mongol invasion in the 13th century. In China it was forbidden in 843, but, although persecuted, it continued there at least until the 14th century. Beliefs similar to Manichaeism appeared during the Middle Ages in Europe in the so-called neo-Manichaean sects. Groups such as the Paulicians (Armenia, 7th century), the Bogomilists (Bulgaria, 10th century), and the Cathari or Albigensians (southern France, 12th century) bore strong resemblances to Manichaeism. Mani and the Manichaeans were fiercely attacked by both the Christian church and the Roman state. Several Church Fathers, such as Serapion of Thmuis, Titus of Bostra, Epiphanius of Salamis, Cyril of Jerusalem, Augustine, John the Grammarian wrote treatises against

Manichaeism, while philosophers also, such as Alexander of Lycopolis and Simplicius, attacked their doctrines. Hence, Manichaeism disappeared almost entirely from western Europe by the end of the 5th century and from the Byzantine empire during the 6th century.

Date Range: 250 CE - 843 CE

Region: Babylonia (southern Babylonia, modern day Iraq)

Region tags: Iraq, Asia, Arabian Peninsula

The region of southern Babylonia the birthplace of Mani, leader of Manichaeans, in the 3rd century CE

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Rea Matsangou, The Manichaeans of the Roman East Manichaeism in Greek anti-Manichaica & Roman Imperial Legislation
- Source 2: Jason D. Beduhn, Paul Dilley, Iain Gardner (ed.), The Medinet Madi Library of Manichaean Codices at 90 Papers from the Symposium at the Chester Beatty Library in Dublin, 18-19 October 2019
- Source 3: Johannes van Oort (ed), Manichaeism and Early Christianity Selected Papers from the 2019 Pretoria Congress and Consultation
- Source 1: Iain Gardner, Jason D. Beduhn, Paul Dilley, The Chapters of the Wisdom of My Lord Mani
- Source 2: Erin Evans, The Books of Jeu and the Pistis Sophia as Handbooks to Eternity. Exploring the Gnostic Mysteries of the Ineffable
- Source 1: Dictionary of Manichaean Texts. Volume III, 2: Texts from Central Asia and China (Texts in Sogdian and Bactrian) Second, Revised and Enlarged Edition Nicholas Sims-Williams, Desmond Durkin-Meisterernst
- Source 2: Greek and Latin Sources on Manichaean Cosmogony and Ethics Samuel N.C. Lieu (ed)
- Source 3: Dictionary of Manichaean Texts. Volume III,4: Texts from Central Asia and China Manichaean Texts in Chinese Gunner B. Mikkelsen
- Source 1: Dictionary of Manichaean Texts. Volume II: Texts from Iraq and Iran (Texts in Syriac, Arabic, Persian and Zoroastrian Middle Persian) François de Blois, Nicholas Sims-Williams
- Source 2: Dictionary of Manichaean Texts. Volume III,1: Texts from Central Asia and China (Texts in Middle Persian and Parthian) Desmond Durkin-Meisterernst
- Source 3: Dictionary of Manichaean Texts. Volume I: Texts from the Roman Empire (Texts in Syriac, Greek, Coptic and Latin) S.N.C. Lieu, S. Clackson, E. Hunter (eds)
- Source 1: Bibliographia Manichaica. A Comprehensive Bibliography of Manichaeism through 1996 G.B. Mikkelsen
- Source 1: In Defence of Faith, Against the Manichaeans Critical Edition and Historical, Literary and Theological Study of the Treatise Aduersus Manichaeos, Attributed to Evodius of Uzalis

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.ekklesiaoflight.com/>
- Source 1 Description: The Ekklesia of Light, modern global Manichaeen Church
- Source 2 URL: <https://imperiumromanum.pl/en/article/policy-of-roman-empire-towards-manicheans/>
- Source 2 Description: Policy of Roman Empire towards Manicheans
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.manichaeism.de/manichaeism/>
- Source 1 Description: Manichaeism
- Source 2 URL: <https://earlychurch.org.uk/mani.php>
- Source 2 Description: Mani (a.k.a Manes) & Manicheism
- Source 1 URL: <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/manichean-art>
- Source 1 Description: Manichaeen Art
- Source 2 URL: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Table-of-Simplified-Manichaeen-Pantheon_tbl1_326274970
- Source 2 Description: Table of Simplified Manichaeen Pantheon
- Source 1 URL: https://heiup.uni-heidelberg.de/journals/index.php/transcultural/article/view/6173/2966#_edn1
- Source 1 Description: Searching for Mani's Picture-Book in Textual and Pictorial Sources. Dr. Zsuzsanna Gulácsi, Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pcxk7M3L6nY>
- Source 2 Description: Zurvan - A Historical Name of God in Manichaeism
- Source 1 URL: <https://whiteink.info/they-executed-mani-and-chased-after-his-supporters-everywhere-the-sassanids-persecuted-manichaeism-in-defense-of-the-religion-of-their-zoroastrian-empire-2/?lang=en>
- Source 1 Description: They executed Mani and chased after his supporters everywhere. The Sassanids persecuted Manichaeism in defense of the religion of their Zoroastrian empire

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://gnosis.org/library/Mani.html>
- Source 1 Description: Manichaeen Scriptures
- Source 2 URL: <http://gnosis.org/library/manis.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Manichaeen Scriptures
- Source 3 URL: <https://sacred-texts.com/chr/giants/giants.htm>
- Source 3 Description: The Book of the Giants
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.azargoshnasp.net/languages/Pahlavi/pahlavi.htm>
- Source 1 Description: Manichaen Middle Persian and Parthian texts
- Source 2 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20081223141441/http://www4.nau.edu/manichaeen/acta.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Acta Archelai. The Acts of the Disputation with the Heresiarch Manes

- Source 3 URL: <http://www.gnosis.org/library/invocbar.htm>
- Source 3 Description: The Invocation of Bar Sîmûs
- Source 1 URL: https://web.archive.org/web/20060629224313/http://www.sant-agostino.it/latino/contro_lettera_mani/index.htm
- Source 1 Description: St. Augustine, Contra Epistolam Manichaei
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.gnosis.org/library/hymndom.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Hymn in honor of the Dominions of Light
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.gnosis.org/library/invocgod.htm>
- Source 3 Description: Invocation of the gods in the Moon
- Source 1 URL: <https://bkv.unifr.ch/de/works/cpg-2510/versions/of-the-manichaeans/divisions>
- Source 1 Description: Alexander von Lykonpolis, Tractatus de placitis Manichaeorum Of the Manichaeans
- Source 1 URL: https://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/03d/1819-1893,_Schaff,_Philip,_2_Vol_04_The_Anti-Manichaeian_And_Anti-Donatist_Writings,_EN.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Augustin: The Writings Against the Manichaeans and Against the Donatists

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Reference: van Oort, Johannes . Mani and Augustine. Collected Essays on Mani, Manichaeism and Augustine. Hammadi and Manichaeian Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2020.

Reference: Gardner, Iain , Paul Dilley, and Jason Beduhn. Mani at the Court of the Persian Kings. Studies on the Chester Beatty Kephalaia Codex. Nag Hammadi and Manichaeian Studies. Leiden: Brill, n.d..

Reference: Bryder, P. . "BUDDHIST ELEMENTS IN MANICHEISM". Encyclopædia Iranica, 2005. <http://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/manicheism-iii-buddhist-elements-in>.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Competitive in the sense of censure and persecution. Apart from the presecution that Manichaeians suffered from Roman and Byzantine emperors, after the participation of Manichaeian adherents in the rebellions against the Song government, all subsequent governments were suppressive against Manichaeism and its followers and the religion was banned in Ming China in 1370.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that the founder of Manichaeism, Mani, incorporated in his teachings many

aspects of Christianity, Judaism and Buddhism, as well as important Jain influence. Mani's extreme degrees of asceticism and some features of Jain doctrine made the influence of Mahāvīra's religious community more plausible than even the Buddha. Furthermore, Mani seems to have been influenced by contemporary Babylonian-Aramaic movements such as Mandaicism, and Aramaic translations of Jewish apocalyptic writings similar to those found at Qumran, and by the Syriac dualist-gnostic writer Bardaisan. Hence, Manichaeism seems to have been doctrinally flexible, so that it could fit and mix with the religions of each region that its adherents spread.

Reference: Lieu, Samuel. *Manichaeism in Mesopotamia and the Roman East. Religions in the Graeco-roman World*. Leiden: Brill, 1999.

Reference: Beduhn, Jason . "Parallels Between Coptic and Iranian Kephalaia: Goundesh and the King of Touran". In *Mani at the Court of the Persian Kings, 52-74*. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2015.
https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004282629_004.

Reference: Dilley, Paul . "'hell Exists, and We Have Seen the Place Where It Is': Rapture and Religious Competition in Sasanian Iran". In *Mani at the Court of the Persian Kings, 211-46*. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2015.
https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004282629_009.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Manichaeism has undertaken its missionary activities with a view to winning the world for the truth of its faith in a well-designed and systematic way. The missionary work is based on a command given to Mani by his spiritual Twin when he had completed his 24th year of life. Therefore, the worldwide mission is inseparably tied with the separation of Mani and his followers from their paternal, Elkhasaite community and with the foundation of the Manichean church. Manichaeans invented a unique way to overcome the cultural and religious difficulties

they met during their missionary activities. The terminological adaptation of Manichean theology to local patterns was an indispensable missionary weapon and proved to be the most effective mean to overcome the gap between the Manichean and alien worldviews, linguistic traditions, and literary means.

Reference: Fiane Teigen, Håkon . "Manichaeen Networks: The Social Networks of the Laity". In *The Manichaeen Church in Kellis. Social Networks and Religious Identity in Late Antique Egypt, 140-77. Nag Hammadi and Manichaeen Studies*. Leiden: Brill, n.d..
https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004459779_007.

Reference: Beduhn, Jason . "not to Depart from Christ!: Augustine Between 'manichaeen' and 'catholic' Christianity". *Harvard Theological Studies* 69, no. 1 (2013): 1-8.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.4102/hts.v69i1.1355>.

Reference: Sundermann, Werner . "MANICHEISM V. MISSIONARY ACTIVITY AND TECHNIQUE". *Encyclopædia Iranica*, 2009. <https://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/manicheism-iv-missionary-activity-and-technique->.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– No

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Boku Tekin (759-780), the ruler of the Uyghur khaganate, converted to the religion in 763. Under his rule, Manichaeism was declared the official religion of the Uyghur state. Boku Tekin promised to the Manichaeen high priests (the Elect) that if they would give orders, he would promptly follow them and respond to their requests. Moreover, during the early caliphates, Manichaeism attracted many followers. It had a significant appeal among the Muslim society, especially among the elites. Sabuhr I

embraced Manichaeism in his effort to seek knowledge. Thus, Manichaeism became popular and flourished throughout the Sasanian Empire.

Reference: Scott, David . "Manichaeism in Bactria: Political Patterns & East-west Paradigms". *Journal of Asian History* 41, no. 2 (2007): 107-30.

Reference: Clark, Louis. "The Conversion of Bugu Khan to Manichaeism". In *Studia Manichaica. IV. Internationaler Kongreß Zum Manichäismus*, 83-123. Akademie Verlag, 2000.

- ↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
 - No
- ↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
 - No
- ↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
 - Yes
- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
 - Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the wide spread of Manichaeism in both East and West, it is difficult to estimate the number of its adherents. However, it seems that Manichaeans were a significant religious force. In 291,

for example, persecution arose in the Sasanian Empire that ended up with the slaughter of many Manichaeans. In the Roman empire, the first official reaction and legislation against Manichaeism, in 302, issued by Diocletian, signifies that there were many adherents. In the mid of 3d century CE Hilary of Poitiers wrote that Manichaeism was a significant force in Roman Gaul and in 381 Christians requested Theodosius I to strip Manichaeans of their civil rights. Furthermore, the Uyghur Khaganate adopted Manichaeism as the official religion of the state for about a century. The spread of Manichaeism in China, Iran, Tibet, the Arab world and Bactria indicates a large number of adherents.

Reference: Matsangou, R. . The Manichaeans of the Roman East: Manichaeism in Greek Anti-manichaica & Roman Imperial Legislation. Leiden: Leiden University , 2021.
<https://hdl.handle.net/1887/3188571>.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Mani was believed to have grown up protected by guardian angels and divine powers, until he met his "Twin" (narzamid in Iranian texts) who enlightened and encouraged him in his missionary activity. Mani's angel, the Didymos (twin), is his spiritual twin, who reveals mysteries to him, helps him and protects him from the traps of Greed and Cunning.

Reference: Teigen, Håkon Fiane . "Manichaean Rituals: Elect and Lay Practices". In The Manichaean Church in Kellis, 215–50. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2021.
https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004459779_009.

Reference: Burkitt, F. Crawford . "The Religion of the Manichees". The Journal of Religion 2, no. 3 (1922): 263-76.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The Manichaean Faith has a traditional hierarchical structure: 1. The Third Messenger, sent by Abba d'Rabbuta (Father of Greatness) is considered the highest spiritual being in our presence. He guides the Council of the Elect. 2. The Prophet Mani was chosen and anointed by God as a prophet to dispense the Message of Light to the world. Manichaeans revere the Prophet and believe him to be among us today. 3. The Arkhegos serves the Manichaean Faith in guiding the flock in the original teachings of Blessed Mani as he originally founded it and as further instructed by the Third Messenger. 4. There are others within the Faith who assist in leading the flock of the children of Light in truth, purity and unity such as overseers, elders and others. The Church itself, with its hierarchy and initiation rituals, had the function of spreading and propagating Mani's teachings, but also guaranteeing the legitimacy of the Elect authorities.

- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Powers are inherited:
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - No
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - No
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - No

Notes: Only a portion of the faithful followed the strict ascetic life advocated in Manichaeism. The community was divided into the elect, who felt able to embrace a rigorous rule, and the hearers who supported the elect with works and alms.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Mani recorded his teachings by writing them. He invented for this reason a unique version of a Syriac script known as the Manichaean alphabet. This is an abjad-based writing system rooted in the Semitic family of alphabets and associated with the spread of Manichaeism from southwest to central Asia and beyond, beginning in the third century CE. It bears a sibling relationship to early forms of the Pahlavi scripts. Unlike Pahlavi, nevertheless, the Manichaean script has influences from the Sogdian alphabet.

Reference: Kara, György. “Aramaic Scripts for Altaic Languages”. In *The World's Writing Systems*, 536–58. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Mani in fact gave his writings a canonical status during his lifetime, since he was afraid of alterations and/or corruption of his teachings.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: No, however, responsible for the dissemination of the manichaean teaching are the Apostles. These are members of the Council of the Elect. They serve the Faith in all fields in bringing the Message of Light to humanity. Apostles offer insights and guidance on a variety of areas affecting the faith of Manichaeans as a whole, and offer insights to the Arkhegos where appropriate. Finally, it is worth mentioning that Manichaeans in the West have founded monasteries.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Manichaeans have nine main books as part of the religion's scripture, seven of which are the "Seven Treatises", which were written by Mani himself in Syriac, one is the "Shabuhrgan", written also by Mani in Middle Persian, and the last one is the "Arzhang", a collection of illustrations created by Mani. There is also a secondary literature called the "Kephalaia", which gives comments and explanations on the scripture, but it is not considered part of the main scripture itself.

Reference: Dilley, Paul , Iain Gardner, and Jason Beduhn. *The Chapters of the Wisdom of My Lord Mani. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies*. Leiden: Brill, 2018.

Reference: Pettipiece, Timothy . *Pentadic Redaction in the Manichaean Kephalaia*. Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2009.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Field doesn't know

Reference: Huashan, Chao . "New Evidence of Manichaeism in Asia: A Description of Some Recently Discovered Manichaean Temples in Turfan". *Monumenta Serica* 44 (1996): 267–315.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/02549948.1996.11731293>.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Reference: Arden-Wong, Lyndon. "Some Thoughts on Manichaean Architecture and Its Applications in the Eastern Uighur Khaganate". In *Between Rome and China, History, Religions and Material Culture of the Silk Road, 181-253*. *Silk Road Studies*. Turnhout: Brepols, 2016.

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The Cao'an temple is a temple in Jinjiang, Fujian, Luoshan Subdistrict in China. Originally constructed by Chinese Manichaeans, it was considered for long as a Buddhist temple. It was considered as the only Manichaean building which has survived intact.

Reference: Lieu, Samuel. *Manichaeism in Central Asia and China*. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 1998.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: The Cangnan Stele is the temple stele of the Yuan Dynasty Manichaean monastery Xuanzhen Temple. It is the sole Manichean stone monument found in the world.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: grottoes

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Painting is a Manichaean tradition that traces its roots back to Mani himself (Arzhang), who elevated art-making to the esteem of the divine spirit, believed that meditating on beauty brought one closer to god, and ultimately saw the practicality of pictures as a transcultural method of teaching. More particular, the "Book of Pictures" is an important book in Manichaeism that shows the idea of light and dark. Mani made the book himself to help people who couldn't read understand his religion. He believed that his religion was better than other religions because it had a book with pictures to explain it, unlike other religions that only had written teachings. The "Book of Pictures" was second only in importance to the "Seven Treatises" in Manichaeism.

Reference: Gulácsi, Zsuzsanna . "Searching for Mani's Picture Book in Textual and Pictorial Sources". *Transcultural Studies* 2, no. 1 (2011): 233–62. <https://doi.org/>: <https://doi.org/10.11588/ts.2011.1.6173>.

Reference: Gulácsi, Zsuzsanna. *Mani's Pictures*. Brill, 2015.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Mani_s_Pictures.html?hl=&id=rUUpCwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Gulácsi, Zsuzsanna . *Mediaeval Manichaean Book Art. A Codicological Study of Iranian and Turkic Illuminated Book Fragments from 8th-11th Century East Central Asia*. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2005.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: On textiles, books, scrolls etc.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: At its core, Manichaeism was a type of gnosticism—a dualistic religion that offered salvation through special knowledge (gnosis) of spiritual truths. Like all forms of gnosticism, Manichaeism taught that life in this world is unbearably painful and radically evil. In Manichaeism inner illumination reveals that the soul, which shares in the nature of God, has fallen into the evil world of matter and must be saved by means of the spirit or intelligence (nous). To know one's self is to recover one's true self, which was previously clouded by ignorance and lack of self-consciousness because of its mingling with the body, i.e. with matter. Thus, to know one's self is to see one's soul as sharing in the very nature of God and as coming from a transcendent world. Knowledge enables people to realize that, despite their abject present condition in the material world, they do not cease to remain united to the transcendent world by eternal and immanent bonds with it. Thus, knowledge is the only way to salvation.

Reference: Neumann, Henry . “Manichaeism Tendencies in the History of Philosophy”. *The Philosophical Review* 28, no. 5 (1919): 491-510. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/2178324>.

Reference: Scem, Hector . “Augustine, the Manichaeism and the Problem of Evil”. *Augustinian Panorama* 5 (1990): 76-86.

Reference: Gardner, Iain. “Dualism in Mani and Manichaeism”. *Dualism in Mani and Manichaeism* 13 (2015): 417-36.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reference: Sundermann, Werner . “A Manichaeon View on the Resurrection of the Body”. *Bulletin of the Asia Institute* 10 (1996): 187–94.

Reference: Ruani, Flavia . “A Robber in Paradise: Luke 23:43 in Manichaeon and Anti-manichaeon Exegesis”. In *Manichaeon and Anti-manichaeon Exegesis.*, 219–49. Nag Hammadi and Manichaeon Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2023.

Reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Reference: Jackson, A. V. Williams . “The Doctrine of Metempsychosis in Manichaeism”. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 45 (1925): 246–68. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/593504>.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Since Manichaeans believed that the soul had to escape from the material world of the body, it seems unlikely that they would have invested in expensive burials and a full traditional treatment of the body. At the same time, their doctrinal position did not result in a negative stance toward the physical body, since they held that health is viewed positively. Nevertheless, there is no evidence pertaining to any sort of treatment of corpses, apart from some Chinese texts that state that Manichaeans ritually undressed their dead and buried them naked within a cloth sack, a practice that has been interpreted in light of the Manichaeon rejection of the body.

Reference: Brand, Mattias. “Matthaios's Grief: Manichaeon Death Rituals”. In *Religion and the Everyday Life of Manichaeans in Kellis*, 230–59. Nag Hammadi and Manichaeon Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2022. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004510296_008.

Reference: Birrel, Michael . “Excavations in the Cemeteries of Ismant El-kharab”. In *Dakhleh Oasis Project: Preliminary Reports on the 1992–1993 and 1993–1994 Field Seasons*, 29–41. Oxford: Oxbow, 1999. https://www.monash.edu/_data/assets/pdf_file/0005/1674041/ismant-cemeteries.pdf.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Only commemorative gatherings and meals after the burial.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Manichaeans knew no lament for the dead, as they believed that the soul was free after its departure from the body. Therefore, death was a joyful event. In a Middle Persian parable, for example, a female catechumen is told explicitly not to mourn over the corpse of her son, as this will kill her

spiritual son. In the Coptic psalms, the singer urges the audience not to weep for the departed, since lamentations hampered the soul in the afterlife, while another psalm calls for celebration. Nevertheless, gatherings at deathbeds, for funerals and in commemoration of the departed took place throughout the Manichaean world. Such gatherings were either rituals to support adherents in their final hours, or a commemoration ritual to aid the journey of their souls through the heavenly spheres. Several of the psalms chanted provide insights into the liturgy of the commemoration, yet almost nothing is known about actual life-cycle rituals such as burials. Furthermore, who participated in commemoration rituals and how frequently they were performed is almost entirely unknown.

Reference: Brand, Mattias. "Matthaios's Grief: Manichaean Death Rituals". In *Religion and the Everyday Life of Manichaeans in Kellis*, 230–59. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2022. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004510296_008.

As cenotaphs:

– Field doesn't know

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There are textual evidence from Manichaean communities in Egypt that attest that burials took place in a certain oasis. The family of the departed would pay the freight costs to transport the body to the oasis, also asking from an Elect to perform a funeral service at the church.

Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Reference: Sundermann, Werner. "THE MANICHEAN PANTHEON". *Encyclopædia Iranica*, 2002. <https://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/manicheism-ii-the-manichean-pantheon>.

Reference: Heuser, Manfred. "Groups of Gods and Ranges of Concepts". In *Studies in Manichaean Literature and Art*, 90–106. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 1998. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004440432_011.

Reference: Sundermann, Werner . "THE MANICHEAN PANDAEMONIUM". *Encyclopædia Iranica*, 2018. <http://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/manicheism-pandaemonium>.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Father of Greatness is the eternal divine manifestation of good in Manichaeism, a four-fold deity, embracing divinity, light, power and goodness. His throne is surrounded by at least 156 peaceful entities: 12 aeons, aeons of the aeons, and angels.

Reference: Giuffré Scibona, Concetta . "How Monotheistic Is Mani's Dualism?". *Numen* 48, no. 4 (2001): 444–67. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/156852701317092896>.

Reference: Shokri-Foumeshi, Mohammad . "I AM ALPHA AND OMEGA. A Jewish-Christian Schema in the Manichaean Context Based on the Middle Iranian Documents in the Turfan Collection". *Religious Inquiries* 7, no. 13 (2018): 35–54.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: Manichaeism rejects everything associated with evil from the Father of Greatness, the Manichaean supreme deity. Neither can he cause suffering nor is he able to charge. He can only defend, therefore his power is limited.

Reference: Denzey Lewis, Nicola. "Ways Out I: Interventions of the Savior God". In *Cosmology and Fate in Gnosticism and Graeco-roman Antiquity*, 127-44. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2013. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004245761_008.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Manichean eschatology, teachings about final things, provided information on what happened during and after the death of a single human being and also on what would happen before and at the end of this world.

Reference: Sundermann, Werner . “Manichean Eschatology”. *Encyclopædia Iranica*, 2012.
<https://iranicaonline.org/articles/eschatology-ii>.

Reference: van Oort, Johannes . “Manichæan Eschatology: Gnostic-christian Thinking About Last Things”. In *Cultures of Eschatology*, 181-93. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2020.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110597745-012>.

Reference: Stroumsa, Guy. “Aspects De L’eschatologie Manichéenne”. *Revue De L’histoire Des Religions* 198, no. 2 (1981): *Revue de l’Histoire des Religions*.

Reference: Koenen, Ludwig. “Manichæan Apocalypticism at the Crossroads of Iranian, Egyptian, Jewish Andchristian Thought”. In *Codex Manichaicus Coloniensis. Atti Del Simposio Internazionale*, 285-332. Cosenza: Marra Editore, 1986.

Reference: Ogden, Charles . “The 1468 Years of the World-conflagration in Manichæism”. In *Dr. Modi Memo-rial Volume. Papers on Indo-iranian and Other Subjects Written by Several Scholars in Honour of Jivanji Jamshedji Modi*. Bombay: The Fort Printing Press, 1930.

Reference: Williams Jackson, A. V. . “A Sketch of the Manichæan Doctrine Concerning the Future Life”. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 50 (1930): 177-98.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - No
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: Nunes Costa, Marcos Roberto . "The Problem of Morality in the Manichaeic Cosmological and Soteriologic System". *Anales Del Seminario De Historia De La Filosofía* 21 (2004): 25–42.
<https://revistas.ucm.es/index.php/ASHF/article/view/ASHF0404110025A>.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Guided by wisdom and by means of a strict vigilance of consciousness, to guard with moral virtues the organs of the five senses, Manichaeans aimed at 'sealing' the perceptions and control their controlling instincts and passions. Manichaeans adopted a medical approach, that helped them to pursue a religious discipline of salvation with practical effects, as far as the self-transformation of the

believer is concerned.

Reference: Teigen, Håkon Fiane . "Introduction: Mani's Church and Social Life". In *The Manichaean Church in Kellis*, 1-27. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2021. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004459779_002.

Reference: Piras, Andrea . "Sealing the Body: Theory and Practices of Manichaean Asceticism". *Religion in the Roman Empire* 4, no. 1 (2018): 28-44. <https://doi.org/10.1628/rre-2018-0004>.

Reference: Fowler, Kimberley. "Characterising Discipleship in the Fifth Manichaean Psalm of Heracleides: Christian Literary Influences and Women's Participation". In *The Chester Beatty Biblical Papyri at Ninety: Literature, Papyrology, Ethics*, 175-91. *Manuscripta Biblica*. Tübingen: De Gruyter, 2023. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110781304-013>.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: In the Manichaean Faith, the family is believed to be a microcosm of the divine order, a reflection of the harmonious balance and unity of the cosmos. It is within the sanctified space of the family unit that Manichaeans learn the virtues of love, compassion, patience, and forgiveness. It is through the bonds of kinship that they find solace, strength, and spiritual nourishment, as they traverse the paths of life.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: One of Mani's three seals, the signaculum sinus" mandates sexual abstinence. After all, sexuality, according to the Manichaeans, is referred to in a highly negative way; sexual desire is the primordial sin and the punishment for sin, which procreates itself by means of the copulation; sexual concupiscence is pre-eminently typical of the kingdom of darkness, the realm of evil, i.e. matter.

Reference: Zafarani, Fahime . Influences of manichaean doctrine on augustine.. Pardisan, Qom, Iran: URD Press, 2017.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Yes

Notes: An interesting reference regarding castration occurs in the fifth homily of John Chrysostom's commentary on Galatians. While discussing Galatians 3:12, in which the Apostle Paul shares his wish that those promoting circumcision among Gentile Christians have the knife slip and castrate themselves, Chrysostom states (In epistulam ad Galatas commentaries 5.3; Greek text in Field 1852:4:83): "If they wish, let them not only be circumcised, but mutilated. Where then are those who dare to castrate themselves, since they draw down the curse, and scandalise the workmanship of God, and take part with the Manichaeans? For the latter call the body treacherous, and from evil matter; and the former by their deeds provide a pretext to these miserable doctrines, cutting off the member as being hostile and treacherous. Ought they not much more to gouge out the eyes, for it is through the eyes that desire enters the soul? But in truth neither the eye nor any other part of us is to blame, but the depraved will only. But if you will not allow this, why do you not cut out the tongue for blasphemy, the hands for theft, the feet for their evil courses and, as to say, the whole body?"

Reference: de Wet, Chris. "John Chrysostom on Manichaeism". *Harvard Theological Studies* 75, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/hts.v75i1.5515> .

Reference: de Wet, Chris. "Manichaeism in John Chrysostom's Heresiology". In *Manichaeism and Early Christianity. Selected Papers from the 2019 Pretoria Congress and Consultation*, 225-52. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2020. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004445468_011.

Reference: Caner, Daniel. "The Practice and Prohibition of Self-castration in Early Christianity". *Vigiliae Christianae* 51, no. 4 (1997): 396-415. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/157007297X00291>.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: The Manichaeans were obliged to observe frequent fasting. Regarding the fasting periods: (1) when the sun is in Sagittarius and the moon is full, they fast two days without break, (2) then when the New Light appears, they fast two days without break, (3) after this, they fast two days when the moon is full (and the sun is) in Capricornus, (4) then when the New Light appears and the sun is in Aquarius and eight days have passed of the (lunar) month, they fast for thirty days, but break the fast each day at nightfall. Furthermore, some Eastern Manichaean sources provide insights about a cycle of communal fasts, culminating in the annual Bema festival, which lasted for four days, likely at the end of a month of

fasting.

Reference: Henning, W. B. . "The Manichæan Fasts". *The Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland* 77, no. 3-4 (1945): 146–64.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S0035869X00099603>.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Mani regarded eating meat as the first major sin of Adam and Eve and he believed that humanity's salvation was only available by rejecting meat, wine, blasphemy, sexuality and work, which all harm light elements. More particular, the Elected, ate mainly fruits and solely drank fruit juices, because they believed that fruit contained many light particles, which is contrary to regular water which was only matter to them. It was forbidden for the Elected to eat or grow plants, to cut down trees or to kill animals.

Reference: Foltz, Richard . *Religions of the Silk Road. Overland Trade and Cultural Exchange from Antiquity to the Fifteenth Century*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 1999.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: An alternative formulation of Mani's three seals divided the ethics of the Elect into Five Commandments: truth, non-injury, chastity, purity of mouth, and poverty. For this reason, the Elect were supposed to possess nothing beyond food for one day and clothing for one year.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

Notes: Only for the Elect.

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Manichaeans observed daily prayers, either four, or seven (for the Elect). Some of these prayers took place after noon, mid-afternoon, just after sunset and at nightfall. The Elect additionally pray at mid-afternoon, half an hour after nightfall and at midnight. Manichaean Elect and catechumens interacted incidentally in various situations. They also prayed together, held their confession rituals, and participated in almsgiving and the ritual meal.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Daily observance of various ritual moments characterized the lives of Manichaeans. Yet, there was a need for time management, hence there was a threefold division of a Manichaean day: one segment of time for government duties, a second for earning one's living, and a third for service to the elect.

Reference: Colditz, Iris . "Manichaean Time-management: Laymen Between Religious and Secular Duties". In *New Light on Manichaeism*, 73–99. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2009. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/ej.97890004172852.i-286.25>.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 8

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Reference: Colditz, Iris . "Manichaean Time-management: Laymen Between Religious and Secular Duties". In *New Light on Manichaeism*, 73–99. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2009. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/ej.97890004172852.i-286.25>.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Circumcision:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: In fact, Mani himself wore colorful clothing, abnormal for his time. However, according to Mani's three seals, the Elect were forced to possess clothing for only one year.

↳ Ornaments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: There is a strong fictive kinship language in Manichaeism. Members of Manichaean communities thought of themselves as bound together by strong ties of spiritual friendship. Their members spoke of each other as sons and daughters of the “Light Mind.” They were inextricably joined one to the other through the common possession of the “Light Mind.”

Reference: Brand, Mattias . “Orion’s Language: Manichaean Self-designation in the Kellis Papyri”. In Religion and the Everyday Life of Manichaeans in Kellis. Beyond Light and Darkness, 125–65. Nag Hammadi and Manichaean Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2022.
https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004510296_005.

Reference: Brown, Peter. Through the Eye of a Needle: Wealth, the Fall of Rome, and the Making of Christianity in the West, 350-550 AD. Eugene OR: Princeton University Press, 2013.

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
 - Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
 - Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Manichaeism spread from the Roman and Byzantine Empire to China. Therefore, the Manichaeans practically belonged in several forms of societies, Empires, states, kingdoms etc.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: This interaction, however, was not always smooth. For example, according to the edict of the Roman emperor Diocletian, promulgated in 302 in Alexandria, the Roman state regarded Manichaeans as Persian spies. Furthermore, Theodosius I stripped Manichaeans of their civil rights, while Justinian persecuted Manichaeans in the 6th century. Apart from persecutions and suppression in the Byzantine Empire, the Manichaeans had no better luck with other regions where the religion spread. In Ming China Manichaeism was banned; during the early Abbasid period, the Manichaeans underwent persecution. The third Abbasid caliph, al-Mahdi, persecuted the Manichaeans, establishing an inquisition. Their

persecution was finally ended in ca. 780. Finally, at the first steps of the Manichaeism religion in the 3d century, after the death of Shabuhr I, Manichaeism met troubles with the heirs of the Persian court.

Reference: BeDuhn, Jason . "Augustine, Manichaeism, and the Logic of Persecution". *Archiv Für Religionsgeschichte* 7 (2005): 153–66.

Reference: Stroumsa, Sarah , and Gedaliahu Stroumsa. "Aspects of Anti-manichaean Polemics in Late Antiquity and Under Early Islam". *The Harvard Theological Review* 81, no. 1 (1988): 37–58.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S0017816000009949>.

Reference: Matsangou, R. . *The Manichaeans of the Roman East: Manichaeism in Greek Anti-manichaica & Roman Imperial Legislation*. Leiden: Leiden University , 2021.
<https://hdl.handle.net/1887/3188571>.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Reference: Escribano, María Victoria . "From Norm to Identity: Christians and Manichaeans in Codex Theodosianus XVI: Separated by the Law". In *Figures D'empire, Fragments De Memoire. Pouvoirs Et Identités Dans Le Monde Romain Impérial (Iie S. Av. N. È.-vie S. De. N. È.)*, 503–29. Villeneuve d'Ascq: Presses universitaires du Septentrion, n.d.. <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.septentrion.68384>.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: A sort of. Manichaeans believe in a series of Principles and Commandments. These are: Do not deny the existence of God (Alaha) or His Oneness. Do not equate God with creation; we believe God is outside time and creation. Do not worship idols. Do not deny that the soul is a spark of the Divine Light. Do not neglect the practice of the Twelve Virtues. Do not use unnecessary force against any person. Do not deny that all men, women, all races, nationalities and sexual orientations are deserving of equality. Do not neglect the practice of protecting all life, including animal life. Do not deny the divine prophethood of Mar Mani and the fact that he is the Apostle of Light. Do not mix magic and false religious beliefs with that of the Prophet Mani. Do not neglect the weekly observance of Shabta, which begins at sundown on Friday and concludes at sundown on Saturday. Do not reject the divine position of the nation of Israel (that it was chosen by God). Do not attempt to interpret the Holy Gospel or any of the teachings given to us by Mar Mani without his teachings in front of you. Do not teach anything contrary to the teachings of the Gospel and do not change their words to mean something than was originally meant. Do not teach that divine revelation is only for one race or ethnic group or nation. Do not elevate one race or ethnicity above that of another. Do not elevate one gender above that of another. Do not abort children, as this is equal to infanticide/murder. Do not sexually abuse children or vulnerable adults; do not withhold information regarding the sin of sexual abuse. If you know of someone who has been or is being sexually abused, it is your duty to report such sin to the proper authorities. Do not reject the practice of alms-giving, for it is a means of salvation for our souls. Do not deny your responsibility to assist your fellow brothers and sisters in the Faith, including widows and orphans, by way of food, shelter or finances, when such assistance is clearly within your means. Do not handle the Gospel, any of the texts sacred to our faith or images of the various Divine Messengers inappropriately; even if it is by mistake, one should repent. Do not neglect the practice of praying at least five times daily. Do not neglect the practice of daily reading of the Holy Book. Do not neglect the regular study of the Holy Book. Do not neglect the practice of fasting as prescribed in our Faith. Do not lie or spread rumors about others. Do not cause a brother or sister to stumble because of your actions or speech. Do not falsely claim to be among the Elect when you are not. Do not steal from others. Do not cause serious harm to the earth. Do not marry or become unevenly yoked with one who questions or denies the existence of God or who has no genuine respect for the Prophet, our Faith or the tenets of our Faith. Do not bully others. Do not make fun of others because of their personal appearance or because of physical handicaps or lack of clothing or funds.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In fact, several Manichaeans participated in peasant movements in China, between the 7th and the 10th centuries, since their religion was used by many rebel leaders to mobilise followers. Manichaean Uyghurs participated in the army of their state during a military campaign in China.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: The Manichaean script is a right-to-left Semitic script, used mainly to write Middle Iranian languages and Uighur (Old Turkish). It is closely related to the Palmyrene script of Aramaic and the Estrangelo script of Syriac. Some of its orthographical conventions are also to be found in the Mandaean script. The Manichaean script was used by adherents of Manichaeism to write texts in Middle Persian, Parthian, Sogdian, Early New Persian, Bactrian, and Uighur. Such texts were mostly found in Central Asia.

Reference: Sundermann, Werner . "The Manichaean Texts in Languages and Scripts of Central Asia". In *Languages and Scripts of Central Asia*. London: Routledge, 1993.

Reference: Durkin-Meisterernst, Desmond . "MANICHEAN SCRIPT". *Encyclopædia Iranica*, 2005. <https://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/manichean-script>.

Reference: Naveh, Joseph. *Early History of the Alphabet. An Introduction to West Semitic Epigraphy and Palaeography*. Leiden: Brill, 1982.

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The Manichaean script is rooted in the Semitic family of alphabets and associated with the spread of Manichaeism from southwest to central Asia and beyond. It resembles to early forms of the Pahlavi scripts. Yet, unlike Pahlavi, the Manichaean script reveals influences from the Sogdian alphabet, which in turn descends from the Syriac branch of Aramaic.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Reference: Durkin-Meisterernst, Desmond . "MANICHEAN SCRIPT". *Encyclopædia Iranica*, online edition, 2005. <http://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/manichean-script>.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: In fact, Manichaeans followed the local formal calendar and they adapted their feasts and their festivals accordingly.

Reference: Sundermann, Werner . "FESTIVALS II. MANICHEAN", 1999. <https://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/festivals-ii>.

Reference: Henning, W. B. . "The Manichæan Fasts". *The Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland* 77, no. 3-4 (1945): 146–64. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S0035869X00099603>.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that Mani included in his moral teaching three seals, two of which, the (a) seal "signaculum oris" (all senses) refers to the prohibition of eating meat, and (b) the seal "signaculum manuum" refers to the way man behaves towards the equine creation, animal and plant kingdom, where man must not harm the world of animals and plants, regulated, so to speak, food production and consumption. Therefore, only a portion of the faithful followed the strict ascetic life advocated in Manichaeism. The community was divided into the elect, who felt able to embrace a rigorous rule, and the hearers who supported the elect with works and alms.

Reference: Pedersen, Nils Arne . "Holy Meals and Eucharist in Manichaean Sources. Their Relation to Christian Traditions". In *The Eucharist - Its Origins and Contexts. Sacred Meal, Communal Meal, Table Fellowship in Late Antiquity, Early Judaism, and Early Christianity, 1265–95*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2017.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know

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